

THE ROLE OF COMMUNITY IN WOMEN'S EMPOWERMENT (Study on the South Tangerang Regional MoM Academy Community)

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze the role of community in women's empowerment within the MoM Academy Regional South Tangerang community. Women in modern society continue to face various social, psychological, and economic challenges that influence their self-development and participation in social life. In this context, women-based communities play an important role in providing social support, self-development opportunities, and empowerment spaces for women. This study employed a qualitative approach with a descriptive method and a constructivist paradigm. Data were collected through in-depth interviews, participatory observation, and documentation studies involving community leaders, administrators, and active members of MoM Academy Regional South Tangerang selected through purposive sampling. The findings reveal that the community functions not only as a social gathering space but also as a medium for women's empowerment through digital training, public speaking, entrepreneurship, and self-development activities. The community successfully builds a strong sense of belonging, emotional support, and interpersonal communication among members. Furthermore, the community contributes positively to increasing women's self-confidence, communication skills, digital competencies, social participation, and economic independence. Women who were previously limited to domestic activities became more confident in expressing opinions, participating in social activities, and generating additional income through digital-based activities and home businesses. The study concludes that MoM Academy Regional South Tangerang plays a significant role as a social support system and agent of social change in strengthening women's empowerment socially, psychologically, and economically. The existence of supportive women's communities is essential in creating inclusive social spaces that encourage women to become more independent, confident, and productive in modern society.

Keywords: Women's Empowerment, Community Role, Social Support, Women Community, Self-Confidence, Economic Independence

INTRODUCTION

Women have a very important role in social, economic, cultural, and family life. In the development of modern society, women are no longer only seen as individuals who play a role in the domestic realm, but also have a great contribution in various sectors of life (Lamphere, 2024). Women are currently increasingly active in education, work, social organizations, and creative economy activities (Gugan et al., 2024). However, social reality shows that women still face various forms of inequality and social pressures that affect their self-development process. Various stereotypes attached to women cause women to often be placed in a lower position than men. Women are considered to be able to meet certain social expectations, such as being a perfect mother, an obedient wife, and maintaining a self-image according to societal standards (Minderop, 2019). This condition often causes psychological, social, and emotional pressure for women in living their lives. Recent studies show that women still experience inequalities in social, economic, and self-development access due to the ever-evolving patriarchal cultural construct in modern society (Azahra et al., 2024). In daily life, women are faced with various demands that arise simultaneously. Women are required to be able to carry out domestic roles while remaining socially and economically productive. On the one hand, women are expected to be able to be soft, patient, and affectionate figures, but on the other hand, women are also required to be strong in facing various life challenges. The pressure is even greater when women begin to compare themselves to the standard of living that is developing on social media. Today's digital phenomenon has

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also created a space that often makes women feel insecure, insecure, and feel inferior to other women. Social labeling regarding beauty standards, household success, and childcare patterns is often a new source of pressure for women. As a result, not a few women experience emotional exhaustion, lose confidence, and even feel that they do not have room to develop according to their potential. Excessive exposure to social media can increase *social comparison* and reduce women's *psychological well-being*, especially in women of productive age (Abdullah et al., 2025). Women who experience persistent social pressure tend to experience decreased self-confidence and social engagement (Guillén et al., 2018). Purnomo (2025) emphasized that digital social pressure is one of the main factors affecting women's mental health in the modern era.

Women's problems are not only related to psychological factors, but also to access to resources and opportunities for development. According to Lamphere (2024), women still experience obstacles in accessing education, economic opportunities, and decision-making positions, especially women who are married and have children. This condition makes it difficult for women to develop their potential and independence optimally. Therefore, women's empowerment is a very important issue to continue to be developed in the life of modern society. Women's empowerment is not only related to economic improvement, but also related to women's ability to build confidence, courage to make decisions, and the ability to participate in social life. Research from Wuryan et al. (2025) shows that women who receive social support and access to training have a better level of economic independence than women who do not receive community support. In addition, Sharma et al. (2020) research explains that community-based women's empowerment is able to improve women's ability to make social and economic decisions.

Women's empowerment is basically an effort to increase women's capacity to be able to develop their potential, improve their quality of life, and have a more equal position in social life. An empowered woman is a woman who is able to recognize her potential, has the courage to express her opinion, is able to make decisions, and has confidence in living life. In this context, the social environment is an important factor that can support the process of women's empowerment. One form of social environment that has a great influence on women's empowerment is community. Azahra et al. (2024) explain that women-based communities have a significant contribution to increasing *self-efficacy*, social solidarity, and women's participation in economic and social activities. In addition, Jacobs & Valentine (2025) also explained that women's communities can be an effective social learning space in building women's identity and confidence. Likewise, the study by Putri & Cahyono (2025) shows that women's social communities have a positive influence on increasing women's self-capacity and digital-based skills.

A community is a group of individuals who have similar interests, goals, values, and experiences that then build social relationships in a sustainable manner. Community presence provides a space for social interaction that creates a sense of security, emotional support, and opportunities to grow. For women, the community is not only a place to gather, but also a space to share experiences, gain new knowledge, and build confidence. Communities are able to provide social relationships that support each other and help women face various challenges in their lives. In a community, women can feel accepted without the social judgments that they have often experienced in the wider community. Research from Sharma et al. (2020) explains that a *sense of belonging* in the community can improve women's psychological well-being and help women reduce social stress due to environmental pressures. Another study from Mhiri et al. (2025) shows that emotional support in women's communities has a significant influence on increasing women's *self-esteem* and *psychological resilience*. In addition, research by Sutanto (2024) explains that interpersonal communication built in women's communities can strengthen social solidarity and increase members' involvement in community activities.

The development of the women's community in Indonesia is currently showing a significant increase. Many women's communities are present with different focuses and goals, such as the housewife community, the working women community, the women entrepreneur community, and the women's self-development community. Despite having different focuses, most of these communities share the same goal, which is to help women become more empowered, confident, and independent. Community presence is important because women need social space that is able to provide emotional support as well as opportunities to develop. Through community, women not only gain new social relationships, but also gain access to information, training, and economic opportunities that can improve their quality of life. Research by Zahro & Khoiriyah (2026) shows that communication in the women's community plays an important role in strengthening solidarity, confidence, and developing women's abilities through supportive social interactions. Research from Trisninawati & Sartika (2024) also confirms that digital-based women's communities are able to improve women's technological literacy skills and expand their social networks. In addition, research by Chen & Barcus (2024) explains that women's communities have a great contribution to building women's motivation to develop household-based businesses.

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One of the women's communities that is active in women's empowerment is MoM Academy. This community is known as one of the largest mothers and women communities in Indonesia which has various regions in a number of regions. MoM Academy exists as a space for women's empowerment that encourages its members to develop, create, and feel more valuable. This community not only provides a space to share stories and experiences, but also presents various skills training that is relevant to the needs of women today, such as digital training, content creators, affiliates, public speaking, and parenting. These programs show that communities have a real role to play in helping women improve their self-capacity. According to Zahro & Khoiriyah (2026), community-based training can improve women's digital capabilities as well as expand household-based economic opportunities. Another study from McCall (2024) also shows that community-based empowerment is able to increase women's economic resilience through strengthening digital skills and community social networks. In addition, research by Visiana (2025) explains that women who are active in self-development communities have higher levels of social participation and economic independence than women who are not involved in the community.

One of the regions that is quite active and developing in the community is the South Tangerang Regional MoM Academy. This region is known as one of the regions that has succeeded in creating various creative programs and producing women who are ready to develop socially and economically. Many community members who previously focused only on domestic activities are starting to gain the courage to develop skills and even generate additional income from home. This condition shows that the community has a considerable influence in helping women rediscover their potential. Communities are not only places of activity, but also social spaces that help women build confidence, improve skills, and gain emotional support from fellow women. In addition, the community also plays a role in building a *sense of belonging* among members. Women who are members of the community feel that they have an environment that is able to accept them without stigma or judgment. Social relationships established through warm communication and intense interaction make women feel more comfortable and not alone in facing various life problems. The community then develops into a social space that is able to strengthen solidarity between women. This is important because many women actually experience loneliness and loss of social space after living a married life. With a community, women have a place to be heard, understood, and valued. Community social support has a significant influence on improving the emotional well-being of married women (Nicolini et al., 2021). Meanwhile, Gyan & Kwakye (2025) emphasized that women's communities are able to increase women's social adaptability and courage in building new social relationships.

The existence of women's communities also has an impact on increasing women's independence. Through various trainings and access to resources, women gain opportunities to improve skills and knowledge relevant to the times. Women are beginning to be able to utilize digital technology and social media as a means of self-development and economic opportunities. The empowerment carried out by the community not only results in economic changes, but also psychological and social changes in women. Women become more confident, more courageous to appear in social spaces, and more able to make decisions in their lives. This process shows that communities have an important role as agents of social change in women's empowerment. McCall (2024) explained that community-based empowerment is able to increase women's *economic resilience* through strengthening digital skills and community social networks. According to Masud-All-Kamal et al. (2021) show that the women's community has a great contribution to improving women's digital-based entrepreneurial skills. In addition, the study by Kalagy et al. (2020) explains that women who are active in social communities have a higher level of independence and confidence in the face of social and economic changes. Based on this phenomenon, research on the role of community in women's empowerment is important. The purpose of this study is to analyze the role of community in women's empowerment at MoM Academy Regional South Tangerang through social support, interpersonal communication, skill development, and increasing women's confidence and independence in social and economic life. Through this research, it is hoped that a deeper understanding of the importance of the role of community in helping women gain space to develop, feel valued, and achieve independence in their lives can be obtained.

METHOD

This study uses a qualitative approach with a descriptive method. The qualitative approach was chosen because this study aims to deeply understand the social phenomenon regarding the role of community in women's empowerment at the South Tangerang Regional MoM Academy. This approach allows researchers to gain a comprehensive understanding of the experiences, views, and social interactions experienced by community members in the process of women's empowerment. According to Creswell & Creswell (2022), qualitative research is used to explore and understand the meaning derived from individuals and groups to a social phenomenon. The descriptive approach is used to describe systematically and factually the role of the community in increasing women's capacity,

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confidence, and independence through various social activities and training carried out by the community. The paradigm used in this study is the constructivism paradigm. The constructivist paradigm views social reality as the result of social constructions formed through experience, interaction, and communication between individuals. In this study, the researcher seeks to understand how community members interpret their experiences while joining the community and how the community shapes the process of women's empowerment through the social interactions that occur in it. The constructivism paradigm was chosen because this research places women's subjective experiences as the main focus in understanding the phenomenon of community-based empowerment (Moleong, 2017; Denzin & Giardina, 2024). The location of the research was carried out at the MoM Academy Regional South Tangerang. The selection of the research location was carried out *purposively* with the consideration that the community is one of the regions that is active in implementing various women's empowerment programs, such as digital skills training, self-development, interpersonal communication, and social activities involving women from various backgrounds. In addition, this community is also considered to have consistent activities in building women's solidarity and independence.

The focus of this research is to analyze the role of community in women's empowerment at MoM Academy Regional South Tangerang which includes: (1) community as a space for women's empowerment, (2) community in building *a sense of belonging* between members, (3) the influence of community on women's social and psychological change, (4) the role of community in meeting women's social and emotional needs, and (5) the impact of community on skill improvement, women's self-confidence, and independence in social and economic life. The research subjects consist of community administrators, *community leaders*, and community members who actively participate in activities at the South Tangerang Regional MoM Academy. The determination of informants is carried out using *the purposive sampling technique*, which is the selection of informants based on certain considerations according to research needs. According to Sugiyono (2022), the purposive sampling technique is used to obtain informants who are considered to understand the phenomenon being researched the most. The criteria for informants in this study include: (1) women who actively participate in community activities for at least six months, (2) administrators or members who are directly involved in women's empowerment programs, and (3) community members who have participated in training or self-development activities organized by the community. The purposive sampling technique was chosen because it is considered to be able to provide relevant and in-depth data according to the focus of the research.

The data collection techniques in this study were carried out through in-depth interviews, participatory observations, and documentation studies. In-depth interviews were conducted to obtain first-hand information about the experiences, views, and changes felt by community members after joining the community. Participatory observation is carried out by observing community activities, interactions between members, and the implementation of women's empowerment programs that take place in the community. Meanwhile, the documentation study was carried out by collecting various documents, photos of activities, community social media, and program archives related to women's empowerment activities. According to Patton (2014), the use of various data collection techniques in qualitative research aims to gain a deeper understanding of the social phenomena being studied. To maintain the validity of the data, this study uses source triangulation techniques and triangulation techniques. Triangulation of sources is done by comparing information obtained from several different informants, such as community administrators and community members. Meanwhile, triangulation techniques are carried out by comparing the results of interviews, observations, and documentation so that the data obtained becomes more valid and credible. According to Miles & Huberman (2020) and Saldaña (2014), triangulation is one of the important techniques in qualitative research to improve the validity of research data.

The data analysis technique in this study uses an interactive analysis model developed by Miles & Huberman (2020) and Saldaña (2014) which consists of three stages, namely data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion drawn. Data reduction is done by selecting, focusing, and simplifying data that is relevant to the focus of the research. The presentation of data is carried out in the form of narrative descriptions so that it makes it easier for researchers to understand the relationships between phenomena found in the field. Furthermore, conclusions are drawn by interpreting the results of the research based on the findings obtained during the research process. Data analysis is carried out interactively and continuously until the data reaches the saturation point (*data saturation*) so that the results of the research can describe the phenomenon in depth and comprehensively.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research result

Community as a Space for Women's Empowerment

Based on the results of observations and interviews, MoM Academy Regional South Tangerang not only functions as a gathering place for women and housewives, but also as an empowerment space that helps women develop their potential. The community provides opportunities for women to gain new experiences, improve their skills, and build confidence through various programs that are held regularly. Activities such as digital training, public speaking, content creators, and self-development are means for community members to improve their personal and social capacity. One of the informants said:

"Informant 1 stated that before joining the community, I was more at home and felt that my abilities were ordinary. After participating in activities at MoM Academy, I became more confident and felt that I could also develop and have skills that could be learned again".

The results of the interviews showed that most members felt that the community provided a safe space for women to thrive without any social pressure or judgment. Many members who previously felt insecure and lacked confidence began to dare to appear, express their opinions, and actively participate in community activities. The community also helps women understand that they have abilities and potentials that can be developed even though they are married and have domestic responsibilities.

Community Builds a Sense of Belonging Among Members

The results of observations and interviews show that MoM Academy Regional South Tangerang has succeeded in building a strong sense of belonging among community members. Community members feel that the community is not just a place to participate in activities, but also a social space that provides a sense of security, comfort, and acceptance. Interactions that are intensely established through community activities make members feel a close emotional connection with other members. One community member explained:

"Informant 2 stated that in this community I feel that I have a new family. If there are problems or are tired of household affairs, here I can tell a story and there must be someone who listens without judgment".

Most of the informants said that the community helped them reduce the loneliness and social pressure they previously felt after living a married life. The warmth of communication, attention between members, and a culture of mutual support in the community make women feel valued and understood.

Community Has a Positive Influence on Women's Personal Change

Based on the results of observations and interviews, the existence of a community has a positive influence on the personal changes of community members. These changes can be seen from the increase in confidence, communication skills, digital skills, and women's courage to try new things. Many members who previously only focused on domestic activities began to dare to take part in training, build social relationships, and even try to earn additional income through social media and household-based businesses. Informant 3 said:

"I used to be afraid to speak in front of a crowd. After participating in several trainings and community activities, now I am more daring to perform and have even been a moderator of community events".

The results of the observations show that the community actively encourages women to continue learning and developing through various training programs that are relevant to the needs of women today. In addition to social changes, psychological changes can also be seen from the increase in confidence and motivation of community members in living their daily lives.

Community Meets the Social and Emotional Needs of Members

The results of observations and interviews show that the community has an important role in meeting women's social and emotional needs. Through warm and supportive interpersonal communication, the community becomes a place for women to share their stories, experiences, and problems in their daily lives. The emotional support provided between members makes women feel calmer and not alone in facing social pressure and domestic problems. Informant 4 said:

"Sometimes women just need to be listened to. In this community, I feel supported and not alone in facing problems as a housewife."

Social interactions within the community help women reduce stress, increase self-confidence, and build positive social relationships. Activities such as *sharing sessions*, recitations, *gatherings*, and casual discussions are

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a means for members to strengthen emotional connections between community members.

Community Provides Access to Resources and Self-Development Opportunities

Based on the results of observations and interviews, MoM Academy Regional South Tangerang provides various access to resources that support women's self-development. The community presents various trainings and classes tailored to the needs of today's women, such as *content creator training*, *digital marketing*, *affiliate marketing*, *public speaking*, and home business development. Informant 5, a community member, explained:

"I didn't initially understand social media for business. After taking affiliate and digital marketing classes, I can now have additional income from home."

In addition to training, the community also opens access to social networks and opportunities for cooperation with various parties, such as *brands*, business actors, and other communities. This provides an opportunity for community members to expand social relations and gain greater economic opportunities.

Community Encourages Women to Be More Confident in Making Decisions

The results of observations and interviews show that the community has a role in increasing women's courage to make decisions and express their opinions. Through a supportive and open environment, women feel more comfortable to express ideas, try new experiences, and be actively involved in community activities. Informant 6 said:

"Previously, I was a quiet person and afraid of making mistakes. After being active in the community, I became more courageous to express my opinions and get involved in activities as a committee."

Such active involvement makes women feel that their existence and opinions are valued. Many members who previously felt afraid or lacked confidence began to dare to make decisions related to their social and economic lives.

Community Helps Women Achieve Independence

Based on the results of observations and interviews, women's empowerment in the South Tangerang Regional MoM Academy can be seen from the changes experienced by community members, both socially, psychologically, and economically. Many women who previously felt incapable began to be able to recognize their potential after joining the community. Informant 7 said:

"This community made me realize that women can also be independent and develop without abandoning their role as mothers. Now I am more confident and can help the family economy from home."

The results of the study also show that communities help women acquire skills relevant to digital development so that women can use social media and technology as opportunities for self-development and additional sources of income. Women not only experience economic changes, but also experience a change in their perspective of themselves. They begin to feel more valued, have a purpose in life, and are more independent in living their daily lives.

DISCUSSION

Community as a Space for Women's Empowerment

The results of the study show that MoM Academy Regional South Tangerang plays a role as a space for women's empowerment that helps community members improve their self-capacity, confidence, and social abilities. Communities are not only a gathering place, but also a means for women to gain new experiences, develop skills, and build awareness that they have the potential to grow. Training programs such as public speaking, content creators, and self-development are tangible forms of women's empowerment carried out by the community. This finding is in line with the concept of women's empowerment put forward by Naila Kabeer that women's empowerment is related to women's ability to gain access to resources, increase their self-capacity, and have the opportunity to make their life choices. Research by Gyan & Kwakye (2025) also explains that women-based communities have a great contribution to increasing women's *self-efficacy* and social participation through social activities and community-based training. In addition, Visiana's research (2025) shows that women's communities are able to be an effective social learning space in improving women's social abilities and identity.

Community Builds a Sense of Belonging Among Members

The results of the study show that the community has succeeded in building a strong sense of belonging among members. Community members feel that the community is a safe, comfortable, and emotionally supportive space. The warmth of communication, attention between members, and a culture of mutual support make women feel accepted without any social judgment. This condition helps women reduce the loneliness and social pressure that

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they often experience after living a married life. The findings of this study support the sense of community theory put forward by McMillan and Chavis that belonging in a community can strengthen an individual's emotional attachment to his or her social group. Minderop's (2019) also explains that the *sense of belonging* in the women's community has a positive influence on psychological well-being and women's ability to deal with social pressure. In addition, Azahra et al. (2024) stated that emotional support built in women's communities can significantly increase women's *psychological resilience* and *self-esteem*.

Community Has a Positive Influence on Women's Personal Change

The results show that community has a positive influence on women's personal change, especially in increasing their confidence, communication skills, and courage to try new things. Many community members who were previously less confident began to dare to appear in public, be active in community activities, and try digital-based economic activities and household businesses. These findings show that communities function as agents of social change that help women build their identity and capacity. McCall's research (2024) explains that community-based women's empowerment is able to increase women's motivation to develop socially and economically. In addition, research by Wuryan et al. (2025) also states that women's involvement in the community can improve women's interpersonal skills, confidence, and social skills in daily life.

Community Meets the Social and Emotional Needs of Members

The results of the study show that the community has an important role in meeting the social and emotional needs of women. The community is a place for women to share their experiences, express their feelings, and gain moral support from fellow community members. This emotional support makes women feel calmer, appreciated, and not alone in facing various life problems. These findings are in line with the research of Trisninawati & Sartika (2024) who explain that interpersonal communication in women's communities has an important role in strengthening solidarity and emotional support between community members. Nicolini et al. (2024) also shows that women who receive social support from the community have better levels of emotional well-being than women who do not have community social support. From the perspective of interpersonal communication, relationships built through empathy and open communication are important factors in creating positive social relationships between community members.

Community Provides Access to Resources and Self-Development Opportunities

The results show that communities provide access to a wide range of resources and opportunities for women's self-development through training and skills development programs. Programs such as digital marketing, affiliate marketing, public speaking, and content creators help women gain new skills that can be used to increase their capacity and economic opportunities. These findings support the research of Gugan et al. (2024) who explain that community-based training is able to improve women's digital capabilities and expand household-based economic opportunities. In addition, research by Sharma et al. (2020) shows that women's communities have a great contribution to increasing women's motivation to develop household-based businesses and the creative economy. The existence of a community also helps women gain access to social networks that can support the development of their businesses and social relationships.

Community Encourages Women to Be More Confident in Making Decisions

The results of the study show that communities help women become more confident in making decisions and expressing their opinions. An open and supportive community environment makes women feel comfortable to share ideas, try new experiences, and be actively involved in community activities. Women who previously tended to be passive began to have the courage to take on roles in community organizations and their social lives. This finding is in accordance with the concept of agency in women's empowerment which explains that empowered women are women who have the ability to make choices and make decisions in their own lives. Lamphere's research (2024) also explains that social support in the community can increase women's courage in making social and economic decisions. In addition, research by Putri & Cahyono (2025) shows that women's involvement in community activities can increase women's social participation and leadership abilities.

Community Helps Women Achieve Independence

The results of the study show that communities help women achieve socially, psychologically, and economically independence. Women who previously felt incapable began to be able to recognize their potential after

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joining the community. Many community members are starting to be able to earn additional income through digital skills and household-based businesses learned through community activities. These findings support the research of McCall (2024) who explains that community-based empowerment can increase women's economic resilience through strengthening community social skills and networks. Research by Masud-All-Kamal et al. (2021) also shows that women's communities have a contribution to improving women's entrepreneurial skills and economic independence. In addition to economic changes, the results of the study also showed psychological changes in the form of increased confidence, life motivation, and women's appreciation for themselves. This shows that women's empowerment is not only related to economic aspects, but also related to changing the way women see themselves as individuals who have values and the ability to develop.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the research that has been conducted, it can be concluded that MoM Academy Regional South Tangerang has a significant role in the process of women's empowerment through social support, interpersonal communication, skill development, and increasing women's confidence and independence. The community not only serves as a gathering place, but also as an empowerment space that helps women develop their potential, gain new experiences, and build awareness that they have the ability to thrive in social and economic life. The results of the study show that the community has succeeded in building *a sense of belonging* and strong emotional connections between community members. The warmth of communication, a culture of mutual support, and a space to share experiences make women feel accepted, appreciated, and not alone in facing various social pressures and problems in domestic life. In addition, the community also has a positive influence on women's personal changes, such as increased confidence, communication skills, courage to express opinions, and motivation to try new things. Through various training and self-development programs, communities also provide access to resources and economic opportunities that help women improve their digital skills and entrepreneurial abilities. Women who previously only focused on domestic activities are starting to be able to utilize social media and digital skills as opportunities for self-development and additional sources of income. This condition shows that the community has a role as an agent of social change that helps women achieve social, psychological, and economic independence. Thus, the existence of the South Tangerang Regional MoM Academy shows that the women's community has an important contribution in creating a supportive social space, increasing women's capacity, and encouraging women to be more confident, independent, and able to develop in the midst of various challenges of modern life.

Based on the results of the research, it is suggested that the South Tangerang Regional MoM Academy continues to develop more innovative and sustainable women's empowerment programs, especially in the fields of digital skills development, entrepreneurship, and strengthening women's mental health. The community is also expected to expand cooperation with various parties, such as educational institutions, the government, and the private sector to open more opportunities for training, mentoring, and economic access for women. In addition, communities need to maintain a supportive and inclusive communication culture so that community members remain comfortable, accepted, and motivated to thrive. For women who are members of the community, it is expected that they can be more active in participating in community activities and taking advantage of various training programs available as a means of self-development and increasing independence. Meanwhile, for the wider community, the results of this research are expected to increase awareness about the importance of the existence of the women's community as a space for social support and women's empowerment in the midst of current social and digital developments. This research still has limitations because it only focuses on one women's community, namely the MoM Academy Regional South Tangerang, so the results of the study have not been able to describe the condition of all women's communities in Indonesia. Therefore, further research is recommended to expand the research object to other women's communities with different characteristics and backgrounds in order to obtain more comprehensive results on the role of communities in women's empowerment. In addition, further research can also use quantitative approaches or mixed methods to measure the influence of community on increasing women's self-confidence, psychological well-being, and economic independence in a more measurable manner. Subsequent research can also develop a focus on the influence of digital media, virtual community communication, and the role of women's communities in building women's social and economic resilience in the digital era.

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THE ROLE OF COMMUNITY IN WOMEN'S EMPOWERMENT

(Study on the South Tangerang Regional MoM Academy Community)

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